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Post-Covid-19 Paradigms in Social Sciences

¹Dr Vinodkumar D. Kumbhar and ²Dr Amol G. Sonawale

This paper aims to suggest the new way for the researchers in the social sciences. The purposive sampling method has been used for this particular study, because the main purpose was, the respondent samples should be aware in the field of social science and he or she should be completed or ongoing his research in social science. The COVID-19 had brought the changes not only in individual but also in society. The researchers, social scientists have also affected by the pandemic and still there is a need to rethinking about the social sciences. The most positive effect of COVID-19 are the social science researchers have found thousands of study areas which needs of fundamental research. The online survey method should be developed and researched. The infrastructural facilities should be increased for the promotion of social science research. At this time the world facing not only problems on human bodies but the COVID-19 has deeply affected on the human mind also. The new methodologies and methods of data collection should be raised after the validity. The social institutions have also changed in their structure and of their structure also. The various concepts of social science should be recited a time to time and it should be do needful changes in these concepts. The new research policies should be launched by the government also. The regular social scientist cannot do much more for society from their busy schedule of rules and regulations. The social sciences should not only elaborate the information, finding of problems, study the reality, but also the social scientist should be work on proper solutions they have to take various projects, problems, operations of society which is needful and fundamental for the development of society.

Keywords: Change in Structure, Change of Structure, Social Science, Paradigms

Introduction

There are four main Paradigms in social science used for to find out the reality of the human society, such as positivism, social constructionism, critical, post-modernism. A paradigm shapes our perspectives about the world as well as the reality. Everyone tries to found the reality as well as facts with the help of specific paradigms. Most of social scientists are engaged in the

examining the concepts which one created by previous Social thinkers. Some concepts are changing on the other hand some things are caused for the change such as COVID-19. The COVID-19 paradigms shifted in social science also.

A paradigm is an explanation about the human society.

A paradigm is an explanation of the relations of human

¹Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Sociology, PDVP Mahavidyalaya, Tasgaon, Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur, MS, India. Email: vinodkumarkumbhar9@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Commerce, PDVP Mahavidyalaya, Tasgaon, Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur, MS, India

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beings. Paradigms are wide perspectives that give access to social scientists define society. It also helps to social scientists to shape hypotheses and finally the theory. A paradigm leads the development of theories.

The main purpose of this research study is to find out the effects of COVID-19 on the social sciences. The social sciences have positive effects of COVID-19 on the other hand have negative effects also. The researcher has discussed both, the positive and negative effects of COVID-19 in this study. The Covid-19 pandemic has been deeply affected on social sciences, research methodologies, paradigms also.

Research Methodology

The researcher used descriptive research design for this particular research work. The purposive sampling

method a form of non-probability sampling has been used for this particular study, because the main purpose was, the respondent samples should be aware in the field of social science and they should be completed or ongoing his research in social science. The data has been collected by the interview schedule as well as formal discussion with the sample respondents. All collected data has been analyzed and the findings and results are discussed in this study. The particular sample respondents have been selected for the opinion about specific paradigm. Such as conflict paradigm, structural functionalism paradigm, Symbolic Interactionism Paradigm. The opinion about the changes in the paradigm and the effects of Covid-19 has been explained in this study.

Table No. 1
Respondent's Views about Paradigms

Paradigms	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Conflict	32	35.55
Structural Functionalism	25	27.78
Symbolic Interactionism	33	36.67
Total	90	100

Figure No. 1
Respondent's Views about Paradigms

The Effects of Covid-19 on the Social Science

Change in Structure

The most positive effect of COVID-19 on the social sciences has found thousands of research study areas. Because the society as well as social institutions has been changing in their structure. The social institutions have also changing their functions. Such as family, the joint family has changed in the form of nuclear family because of urbanization, industrialization, globalization, but the COVID-19 has shifted the new changes, need of the joint family, importance of joint family. In the disaster most of people migrated from the city, urban areas to rural area at their native place. So various social institutions are changing rapidly in the COVID-19 era, such as family, education, religion, economy, state, marriage etc.

Scope

There are short-term as well as long-term effects of COVID-19 pandemic on social sciences the scope for various study fields have been raised. for example, disaster management, disaster studies etc. The COVID-19 pandemic situation demanded the rethinking the various aspects of social sciences such as concepts, theories, assumptions, research methodology, tools of data collection etc.

Public sphere

The COVID-19 conditions reveal to rethink on the concept of 'public sphere' it have to be rethink and re-shaped. Because such conditions can be made in future also. The Covid situation restricted about the public spaces and social activities. So most of people have turned towards online facilities and digital world. Various social media and websites, applications have provided the facilities of social interaction through digital media, such as zoom, Google meet etc. The COVID-19 had brought the changes not only in individual but also in society. The researchers, social scientists have also affected by the pandemic and still there is a need to rethinking about the social sciences. The most positive effect of COVID-19 is the social science researchers have found thousands of study areas which needs of fundamental research. The role of social sciences has to be rethinking or revised for post- pandemic society.

The Role of Social Sciences

The Conflict Paradigm

The Conflict Paradigm explains the concept of Socialization, Social Structure, Bureaucracies, Deviance, Inequality, Family, Education, Religion etc. As per the Conflict Paradigm the Social Structure is the set of the elementary unit of society as well as its analysis also. It exists in time and space. The social structure is objective. As per the Conflict Paradigm roles, groups, status, institutions are exists for the security of maintenance of the elite. There is a conflict over power, status and wealth.

Government Policies

The research policies launched by government also affect to the researchers, thinkers of social sciences. The regular teachers cannot do spend more time on research, because of regular duties of their teaching profession. So the new policy should be launched for the social science teachers, who can be spent more time on the research. At the present, the role of social science is to study the social fact. But this era after Covid-19 needs not only to study the social fact but the solutions of the social problems also.

The infrastructural facilities

The infrastructural facilities should be increased for the promotion of social science research. At this time the world facing not only problems on human bodies but the COVID-19 has deeply affected on the human mind also. The COVID-19 had brought the changes not only in individual but also in society. The social institutions have also changed in their structure and of their structure also.

Methodological Aspects

Concepts of social science

The various concepts of social science should be recited a time to time and it should be do needful changes in these concepts. The concepts about to study the society should be rethinking. These concepts need the time to time changes.

Most of qualitative research had been affected because of Covid-19 pandemic situation. Most of empirical research investigations had been stopped even the field

work, case studies had slowed. The social researchers had restrictions during Covid -19 situation. It is a fundamental issue faced by Social Science. The qualitative research had been challenged also. At that time most of researchers had been adopted online tools of data collection. Such as videoconferencing but it is not a proper solution of all the issues. The Covid-19 is a collective dilemma for the social sciences as well as pure sciences. So the time has come for social sciences to rethinking of concepts, methodologies, various approaches used for understanding the social reality. The digital tools of the data collection should be developed and used by social scientists. The digital tools of data collections can be developed by use of ICT. Such as online interview, but still it has a limitations to organize the participative observation. The online survey method should be developed and researched.

Research policies

The new research policies should be launched by the government also. The regular social scientist cannot do much more for society from their busy schedule of rules and regulations.

Role of Social Scientists

The social sciences should not only elaborate the information, finding of problems, study the reality, but also work on proper solutions. They have to take various projects, problems, operations of society which is needful and fundamental for the development of society.

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